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The first batch of compensated LGAD sensors

V. Sola ^{a,b,*}, G. Paternoster ^{c,d}, A. Morozzi ^e, R. Arcidiacono ^{f,b}, M. Barozzi ^{c,d}, G. Borghi ^g,
 M. Boscardin ^{c,d}, N. Cartiglia ^b, M. Centis Vignali ^{c,d}, M. Costa ^{a,b}, T. Croci ^e, M. Ferrero ^b,
 A. Fondacci ^h, F. Ficorella ^{c,d}, S. Giordanengo ^b, O. Hammad Ali ^{c,d}, C. Hanna ^{a,b}, L. Lanteri ^{a,b},
 L. Menzio ^b, F. Moscatelli ^{i,e}, D. Passeri ^{h,e}, N. Pastrone ^b, F. Siviero ^b, R.S. White ^b

^a Università degli Studi di Torino, via P. Giuria 1, 10125, Torino, Italy^b INFN, Sezione di Torino, via P. Giuria 1, 10125, Torino, Italy^c Fondazione Bruno Kessler, via Sommarive 18, 38123, Povo (TN), Italy^d TIFPA-INFN, via Sommarive 18, 38123, Povo (TN), Italy^e INFN, Sezione di Perugia, via A. Pascoli, 06123, Perugia, Italy^f Università del Piemonte Orientale, largo Donegani 2/3, 28100, Novara, Italy^g Politecnico di Milano, via Ponzio 34/5, 20133, Milano, Italy^h Università degli Studi di Perugia, via G. Duranti 93, 06125, Perugia, Italyⁱ CNR-IOM, via A. Pascoli, 06123, Perugia, Italy

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ABSTRACT

A new development of radiation-resistant silicon sensors is presented. The new sensors exploit the Low-Gain Avalanche Diode (LGAD) technology, with internal multiplication of the charge carriers, in combination with thin substrates, intrinsically less affected by radiation. An innovative design of the gain implant typical of the LGADs has been developed and fabricated, employing the compensation of acceptor and donor dopants to reproduce the effective acceptor doping dose of standard LGAD sensors.

At the end of 2022, the Fondazione Bruno Kessler (Italy) delivered the first batch of compensated LGAD sensors on 30 μm thick p-type epitaxial substrates. Electrical and transient characterisation of the sensors has been performed before and after irradiation up to $5 \cdot 10^{15}$ 1 MeV equivalent n/cm².

The ultimate goal is to develop and produce compensated LGAD sensors that can efficiently operate above fluences of 10^{17} 1 MeV equivalent n/cm².

1. Introduction

The next generation of high-energy and high-intensity hadron colliders for particle physics will require tracking detectors able to efficiently record charged particles in harsh radiation environments, where the expected fluences¹ exceed 10^{17} n_{eq}/cm² [1,2].

Recently, thin Low-Gain Avalanche Diodes (LGADs) [3], with an active thickness of ~ 50 μm , have proven their ability to combine precise timing with precise tracking measurements, making them suited candidates for 4D tracking in future experiments [4]. At present, the gain mechanism of LGAD sensors under irradiation is maintained up to a fluence of $2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ n_{eq}/cm² [5].

To enable the usage of LGADs in the extreme fluence regime, an innovative design of the LGAD gain layer, the p⁺ implant responsible for the local and controlled signal multiplication, has been implemented to

enhance their radiation tolerance by more than one order of magnitude: the compensated LGAD [6].

In the standard LGAD design, the gain layer is obtained by implanting $\sim 5 \cdot 10^{16}$ atoms/cm³ of an acceptor dopant in the region below the n⁺ electrode. In the compensated design, the gain layer results from the overlap of a p⁺ and an n⁺ implant: the difference between acceptor and donor doping will bring an effective concentration similar to standard LGADs. The new design will be more resilient to radiation, as both acceptor and donor atoms will undergo removal with irradiation, but if properly engineered, their difference will remain constant. Therefore, the compensated LGADs will empower the 4D tracking ability to fluences above 10^{17} n_{eq}/cm².

The first production of compensated LGAD sensors was released by the Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) foundry at the end of 2022. Electrical characterisation and signal analysis from compensated LGAD

* Corresponding author at: Università degli Studi di Torino, via P. Giuria 1, 10125, Torino, Italy.

E-mail address: valentina.sola@unito.it (V. Sola).

¹ Along the document, the fluence unit is n_{eq}/cm², as the abbreviation for 1 MeV equivalent n/cm².

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Fig. 1. (a) Sketch of a compensated LGAD sensor. The black dotted rectangle indicates the portion of the sensor investigated with Silvaco and SIMS. The drawing is not to scale. (b) Doping profiles of the simulated implants in a compensated LGAD [6] using TCAD Silvaco [8]. The light blue line indicates the Boron concentration, the blue line is the Phosphorus concentration, and the red line represents the total effective doping in absolute value. The dopant concentrations are also expressed through the colour fill. (c) Doping profiles of the simulated implants in a compensated LGAD as extracted from SIMS. The colour coding is the same as in (b).

Table 1

Split table of compensated LGAD wafers with/ gain implant doses. For the dose coding presented in the table, $a < b < c$ and $2c < 3a$. Also, a wafer with the standard design of the gain implant is reported as a reference, W5.

Wafer #	p^+ dose	n^+ dose	C dose
5	1	–	1
6	2a	1	–
7	2b	1	–
8	2b	1	–
9	2c	1	–
10	3a	2	–
11	3b	2	–
12	3b	2	1
13	3b	2	–
14	3c	2	–
15	5a	4	–

sensors before and after irradiation with neutrons up to $5 \cdot 10^{15} n_{eg}/cm^2$ will be presented and discussed in the following Sections.

2. Production of compensated LGAD

The first production of compensated LGAD sensors was completed at FBK in November 2022.

The compensated LGAD sensors have been fabricated on 6-inch epitaxial wafers with an active thickness of $30 \mu m$ in the framework of the EXFLU1 batch [5,7]. The wafers' description is reported in Table 1.

Three different combinations of acceptor and donor doses have been investigated in the batch, namely 2–1, 3–2, and 5–4. For the first two combinations, three different doses of p^+ concentration have been used, to optimise the dose of acceptor to be compensated by the donor. Boron has been used as the acceptor dopant, and Phosphorus is the donor one. For one wafer of the combination 3–2, also Carbon has been co-implanted together with Boron and Phosphorus, to investigate its effect in mitigating the Boron deactivation with irradiation [4,9] when also Phosphorus atoms are present in the same volume. Dose 1 of Carbon has been used, relative to the FBK scaling.

Fig. 1 (a) and 1 (b) show the sketch of a compensated LGAD sensor and the doping concentration of a compensated gain implant for the 5–4 case as obtained from the process simulation made with the Silvaco Technology CAD tool [8], respectively.

3. Characterisation of the compensated LGADs before irradiation

Extensive electrical characterisation and tests have been performed on the wafer and after dicing. In the following, measurements of the dark current as a function of the reverse bias and signal analysis from infrared laser stimulus are presented.

3.1. Dark current from compensated LGAD sensors

First quality tests and electrical investigations were performed on the wafer at FBK before dicing. The measurement campaign concentrated on sensors with an LGAD and a PIN on the same die, with an active area of $0.75 mm \times 0.75 mm$ each. Measurements were performed at room temperature.

Fig. 2(a) shows the dark current as a function of the reverse bias for different compensation of $p^+ - n^+$ doping obtained from the device simulation with the Synopsys Technology CAD tool [10]. The simulation takes as an input the doping profiles from the device simulation. The standard LGAD case ($p^+ \times 1$) is included in the comparison. For all the compensated combinations, it is possible to obtain an electrical behaviour similar to the standard LGAD sensors, with an initial rapid increase of the dark current due to the depletion of the gain implant region, followed by a steep increase due to the depletion of the bulk, and once the sensors are fully depleted, the exponential growth of the dark current typical of LGADs is observed, following the impact ionisation relationship that links the charge multiplication with the reverse bias increase [11].

Figs. 2 (b), 2(c), and 2(d) show the dark current as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD sensors before dicing for dopant compensation differences of 2–1, 3–2, and 5–4, respectively. In all figures, measurements from a PIN and a standard LGAD sensor from the same batch are shown for comparison. In the case of 2–1 compensation, all wafers exhibit a rapid increase of the current at a very low bias of $\sim 25 V$, corresponding to the sensor depletion in the standard LGAD case. For 3–2 compensation, the dark current has an almost flat behaviour up to about $50 V$, and then a rapid increase of the current with bias is observed. The wafers with a higher Boron dose (e.g., W14) show an earlier increase in the current behaviour. Also, the carbonated wafer (W13) has a delayed increase of the current with bias, as it was already observed in standard LGADs [12]. For W15 (5–4), the behaviour is similar to the 3–2 case, but the current increase happens at a much higher bias, at $\sim 170 V$.

The difference between the predicted dark current behaviour shown in Fig. 2(a) and the experimental curves in Figs. 2 (b), Figs. 2 (c), and Figs. 2 (d) is due to a non-optimal calibration of the real Boron and Phosphorus profiles, with respect to the simulated ones. Fig. 1(c) displays the profiles extracted from W15 (5–4) using Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) [13]. After the production process, the dopant profiles resulted broader than the simulated one in Fig. 1(b). In particular, the Boron implant is closer to the n^{++} contact and has a lower peak concentration, while the Phosphorus implant is higher than the simulated one.

Fig. 3(a) shows the dark current as a function of the reverse bias measured on single pads with an active area of $1.3 mm \times 1.3 mm$ after dicing. Measurements were performed at a fixed temperature of $+20^\circ C$. The results are in good agreement with the ones obtained on the wafer at FBK.

Fig. 2. Dark current as a function of the applied reverse bias as simulated by TCAD Synopsys [10] (a) for different combinations of Boron and Phosphorus densities and as measured on wafers at FBK for the Boron–Phosphorus differences 2–1 (b), 3–2(+C) (c), and 5–4 (d). The dark currents from a PIN sensor and a standard LGAD (W5) from the same batch are shown as a reference.

Fig. 3. (a) Dark current as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD sensors after dicing. The curve from W6 (2–1) is magenta, W12 (3–2) is blue, W13 (3–2+C) is light blue, and W15 (5–4) is green. The dark currents from a standard LGAD and a PIN sensor from the same batch are shown in black as a reference. (b) Simulated dark current as a function of the reverse bias using doping profile obtained from SIMS on W15 (5–4).

Fig. 3(b) show the simulation with the TCAD Synopsys tool [10] using the W15 profiles obtained from SIMS as input. The simulation has been performed at the temperature of +25 °C, the same active area of sensors has been considered, and the Massey model [14] of impact ionisation has been used. The different bias value at which the rapid increase of the dark current is observed with respect to the data can be due to the difference between the tails of the effective dopant profiles and the ones extracted by the SIMS. The similar shape observed in data and simulation confirms the predictive power of the simulation tool.

3.2. TCT scan of a compensated LGAD

A signal analysis over the sensor surface was executed to investigate if the source of the high current is localised in a specific region of the sensor.

Signal measurements are performed through a Transient Current Technique (TCT) setup, inducing a signal into the sensors using an infrared picosecond laser with a wavelength of 1060 nm. The laser can be focused with a lens, and the minimum diameter of the laser spot is 10 μm . The sensor output signal is amplified by a 40 dB Cividec Broadband Amplifier, a low-noise current amplifier with an analogue bandwidth of 2 GHz, and readout by a Teledyne Lecroy Oscilloscope (740Zi) with a sampling of 40 GSamples/s and a bandwidth of 4 GHz.

A sensor from W12 (3–2) with an active area of 0.98 mm \times 0.98 mm and no metal above the active region, except for the four corners of the

pad, was investigated. A reverse bias of 81 V was applied to the sensor, very close to the breakdown condition, to spot regions with a high electric field, where signals can appear with a higher amplitude with respect to regions with moderate electric fields [15]. A 2D scan with the picosecond infrared laser was performed, and the result is reported in Fig. 4. Hot spot regions are not visible in the Figure. In particular, in the region along $x \sim 390 \mu\text{m}$, and $y \sim 190 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to the periphery of the gain implant where Boron and Phosphorus implants could have a different lateral diffusion close to the junction termination extension and cause an abrupt increase of the electric field, the signal amplitude is small. In particular, the signal amplitude scales with the radial distance from the readout pad. Therefore, it can be deduced that the signal multiplication happens in the region between the gain implant and the n^{++} contact, as expected by the LGAD design.

3.3. Gain of compensated LGAD sensors

The same setup utilised for the 2D scan was employed to measure the gain of compensated LGAD sensors as a function of the reverse bias.

Test samples with an LGAD and a PIN sensor in the same die, with an active area of 0.75 mm \times 0.75 mm each, were used for the measurement.

The PIN diode is used to calibrate the signal to the one obtained from a minimum ionising particle (MIP) crossing the sensors, which, for an active thickness of 30 μm , is expected to generate a signal of ~ 0.3

Fig. 4. 2D scan of a compensated LGAD sensor not covered with metal. On the left, the layout of the sensor is shown, with the detail of the scanned area. On the right, the area of the signal resulting from the x-y scan is visible, with the sensor layout superimposed.

Fig. 5. Gain as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD illuminated with an infrared laser. The curve from W6 (2–1) is magenta, W12 (3–2) is blue, W13 (3–2+C) is light blue, and W15 (5–4) is green. The gain from a standard LGAD sensor from the same batch is shown in black as a reference. All measurements are performed at a laser intensity equivalent to about 4 MIPs. The temperature of operation for each measurement is indicated in the legend.

fc [16]. The gain of the LGAD sensors is obtained by illuminating both the PIN and the LGAD with the infrared laser set at the same intensity and using the relation:

$$G = \frac{LGAD \text{ Signal Area}}{\langle PIN \text{ Signal Area} \rangle}, \quad (1)$$

where the average of the measured areas of the PIN signals taken at different bias voltages is used as the denominator.

The results of the gain measurement are shown in Fig. 5. The gain from a standard LGAD sensor from W5 is reported as a reference. All the Boron–Phosphorus compensated combinations exhibit flat gain close to unity, then a sudden increase of the gain, followed by a decrease, never observed in the case of standard LGAD sensors. W6 exhibits a further increase in the gain before the current breakdown is reached.

Two waveforms from the gain measurement on W6 are shown in Fig. 6, taken at two different values of bias voltage. The original signals are negatives and have been inverted for aesthetic purposes only. The signals from compensated LGAD sensors exhibit a fast rise and a time duration of about 2 ns, comparable to signals from the standard LGADs. The ripple observed after the signals appear only on cold measurements, and could be induced by the cooling system.

Fig. 6. Two waveforms from the W6 sensors tested with TCT at a temperature of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The operating bias voltage is -30 V (plum line) and -40 V (salmon line), respectively.

4. Characterisation of the compensated LGADs after irradiation

Irradiation of compensated LGAD sensors was done at the JSI TRIGA Mark II neutron reactor [17] from a fluence of $4 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ to $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$.

4.1. Dark current from compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation

The dark current of compensated LGAD sensors was measured after irradiation up to $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ on single pad sensors with an active area of $1.3 \text{ mm} \times 1.3 \text{ mm}$ from four different wafers, namely W6 (2–1), W12 (3–2), W13 (3–2+C), and W15 (5–4). Measurements of irradiated sensors were performed at a fixed temperature of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and are compared to the corresponding measurements taken before irradiation, as shown in Fig. 7. It is worth noting that it is difficult to measure currents below 100 pA.

The expected increase of the dark current with irradiation is observed [4] due to the defects created in the active bulk of the sensors. However, with increased fluence, the flat current behaviour followed by a steep increase is mitigated, and, at the highest fluences, the current behaviour is more similar to the one of standard LGAD, where at low bias, the current is low, due to the depletion of the gain implant volume, followed by a linear increase before breakdown multiplication.

Therefore, with irradiation, the behaviour of compensated LGADs becomes similar to standard LGAD sensors. Still, the increase of the current with bias, due to internal multiplication, seems to be maintained up to the highest fluences, showing a higher resilience to irradiation with respect to standard LGADs [5].

4.2. Capacitance of compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation

For the sensors investigated in the previous Section, measurements of the capacitance as a function of the reverse bias voltages (C-V) were performed at a temperature of $+20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a frequency of the sinusoidal signal of 2 kHz and are shown in Fig. 8. The measurements were also performed at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 500 Hz, confirming the observed behaviour.

As for silicon diodes, a compensated LGAD with an applied reverse bias can be considered a parallel plate capacitor, where the distance between the capacitor plates is the width of the depleted region, and the area of the plates corresponds to the active area of the sensors. The capacitance C of the sensor is related to the reverse bias V and the effective active doping concentration N_{eff} , as given by the relation:

$$C \propto \sqrt{N_{eff}/V}. \quad (2)$$

The capacitance curves of compensated LGAD are difficult to interpret. Before irradiation, only W6 (2–1) shows a little bump between

Fig. 7. Dark current as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation from $4 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ to $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ for W6 (2–1), W12 (3–2), W13 (3–2+C), and W15 (5–4). The measurements are performed at a temperature of $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 8. Capacitance as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation from $4 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ to $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ for W6 (2–1), W12 (3–2), W13 (3–2+C), and W15 (5–4). All the measurements are performed at a temperature of $+20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a frequency of 2 kHz .

0 and 25 V in the region where the depletion of the gain layer is expected; for higher bias, the current inside the sensors becomes too high to obtain meaningful results. For higher concentrations of Boron–Phosphorus, the capacitance measurement has a trend similar to PIN sensors. Only with increasing irradiation, the capacitance recovers the LGAD behaviour, measuring a high concentration of N_{eff} . For W12 (3–2) and W13 (3–2+C), at the fluence of $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$ the standard C-V shape is restored. For W15 (5–4), higher fluences are necessary to properly observe the C-V bump at a low bias typical of the gain implant region.

4.3. Gain of compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation

Irradiated LGAD sensors with the same LGAD-PIN geometry as the ones presented in Section 3.3 were used to investigate the gain performances of compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation.

The gain definition has been updated for the irradiated case according to the relation:

$$G = \frac{LGAD \text{ Signal Area}}{\langle PIN \text{ Signal Area}^{NO \text{ gain}} \rangle}, \quad (3)$$

where the average of the measured areas of the PIN signals are taken at bias voltages below 400 V, as above this value signal multiplication in the bulk region occurs.

The gain as a function of the reverse bias is shown in Fig. 9 for sensors of W12 (3–2) and W13 (3–2+C) irradiated at different fluences. The tests were performed at a temperature of about $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the infrared laser intensity equivalent to $\sim 4 \text{ MIPs}$. For unirradiated sensors, only the rising part of the curve is considered (see Fig. 5) for the sake of clearness. Despite W12 and W13 having similar behaviour before irradiation, once irradiated W13 exhibit a higher gain with respect to W12. In particular, at the same bias voltage, sensors from W13 have a gain of three times higher than sensors from W12 irradiated at the same fluence.

From this gain analysis, it is possible to conclude that the co-implantation of Carbon in the region of the gain implant mitigates the deactivation of Boron atoms even in compensated LGAD sensors, where

Fig. 9. Gain as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD illuminated with an infrared laser. The measurements are from W12 (3–2) as triangles and W13 (3–2+C) as diamonds before and after irradiation up to the fluence of $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$. The measurements are performed at a temperature of -20°C and at a laser intensity equivalent to 4 MIPs.

Fig. 10. Gain in blue and timing resolution in red as a function of the applied reverse bias for compensated LGAD from β source. The measurements are from W12 (3–2) after irradiation to the fluence of $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$. The measurements are performed at a temperature of -25°C .

also Phosphorus atoms are implanted in the same volume. Therefore, the presence of Phosphorus does not alter the effect of Carbon co-implantation, which maintains the same effect as in standard LGAD sensors [4].

4.4. β Test on compensated LGAD sensors after irradiation

A single pad from W12 (3–2), with an active area of $1.3 \text{ mm} \times 1.3 \text{ mm}$ and irradiated to $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$, was tested with β particles.

Measurements have been performed at -25°C . The signal from the compensated LGAD is read through a UCSC board followed by a 20 dB Cividec Broadband Amplifier and analysed by a Teledyne Lecroy Oscilloscope (9254M) with a sampling of 40 GSamples/s and a bandwidth of 2.5 GHz. The timing reference is an MCP-PMT produced by Photonis with a timing resolution of about 15 ps. Only β particles that cross the full sensor thickness of about $650 \mu\text{m}$ are considered to make the energy released in the active volume comparable to a MIP.

Fig. 10 shows the gain and the timing resolution, σ_t , of the W12 irradiated sensor for four different values of reverse bias voltages. For higher bias, the noise of the system increased, and it was not possible to distinguish the signals from the noise floor. For the measured point, the root mean square of the noise ranged from 1.4 to 1.7 mV. The measured timing resolution goes from 51 to 38 ps, for gain ranging between 7 to 13. The corresponding collected charge varies from 2 to 4 fC.

From the test with β particles, it is possible to conclude that compensated LGAD sensors have timing performances similar to standard LGADs [4].

5. Conclusion

The first batch of $p^+ - n^+$ compensated LGAD sensors was released by FBK at the end of 2022. Three different strategies of Boron–Phosphorus concentration are investigated, namely 2–1, 3–2 with one carbonated wafer, and 5–4.

The electrical behaviour of compensated LGAD sensors differs from the standard LGADs due to a difference in shape and concentration between the Boron and Phosphorus implants from the process simulation and those resulting from the production process. However, gain measurements indicate that the signals from compensated LGADs are identical to the ones from the standard design.

Compensated LGAD have been irradiated with neutrons of up to $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$. After irradiation, a certain amount of Boron and Phosphorus atoms become inactive. Due to this process, electrical and transient behaviour similar to standard LGAD sensors is retrieved at the highest fluences.

After comparing the gain performances of W12 (3–2) and W13 (3–2+C), it can be concluded that Carbon co-implantation helps to prevent the acceptor removal by a factor of 3. This is even true when donor atoms such as Phosphorus are present within the same volume.

Testing a compensated LGAD sensor irradiated to $2.5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$, a timing resolution of 38 ps has been reached at a moderate gain of 13. This result indicates that compensated LGADs can reach timing performances comparable to the standard LGAD sensors.

The EXFLU1 batch represents the first step towards the development and production of silicon sensors that can efficiently operate above fluences of $10^{17} \text{ n}_{eq}/\text{cm}^2$. Other batches of compensated LGAD sensors with dopant implants further optimised in shape and concentration will be released by FBK in the future years.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- [1] International Committee for Future Accelerators, URL <https://icfa.hep.net/>.
- [2] ECFA Detector R&D Roadmap, URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.17181/CERN.XDPL.W2EX>.
- [3] G. Pellegrini, et al., Technology developments and first measurements of low gain avalanche detectors (LGAD) for high energy physics applications, Nucl. Inst. Meth. A 765 (2014) 12–16, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2014.06.008>.
- [4] M. Ferrero, et al., An Introduction to Ultra-Fast Silicon Detectors, CRC Press, 2021, p. 196, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1201/9781003131946>.
- [5] R.S. White, et al., Characterisation of the FBK EXFLU1 thin sensors with gain in a high fluence environment, in: 43rd RD50 Workshop on Radiation Hard Semiconductor Devices for Very High Luminosity Colliders, CERN, 2023, URL <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1334364/contributions/5672078/>.
- [6] V. Sola, et al., A compensated design of the LGAD gain layer, Nucl. Inst. Meth. A 140 (2022) 167232, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2022.167232>.
- [7] V. Sola, et al., Characterisation of the EXFLU1 batch from FBK, in: 42nd RD50 Workshop on Radiation Hard Semiconductor Devices for Very High Luminosity Colliders, Tivat (Montenegro), 2023, URL <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1270076/contributions/5450195/>.
- [8] SILVACO, Semiconductor Process and Device Simulation, URL <https://silvaco.com/tcad/>.
- [9] M. Ferrero, et al., Radiation resistant LGAD design, Nucl. Inst. Meth. A 919 (2019) 16–26, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.11.121>.

- [10] Synopsys TCAD, Device Simulation, URL <https://www.synopsys.com/silicon/tcad/device-simulation.html>.
- [11] W. Maes, K. De Meyer, R. Van Overstraeten, Impact ionization in silicon: A review and update, *Solid-State Electron.* 33 (1999) 705–718, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101\(90\)90183-F](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101(90)90183-F).
- [12] V. Sola, et al., First FBK production of 50 ultra-fast silicon detectors, *Nucl. Inst. Meth. A* 924 (2019) 360–368, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.07.060>.
- [13] A. Benninghoven, F.G. Rudenauer, H.W. Werner, Secondary ion mass spectrometry: Basic concepts, instrumental aspects, applications and trends, 1987, URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/6092161>.
- [14] D.J. Massey, et al., Temperature Dependence of Impact Ionization in Submicrometer Silicon Devices, *IEEE Trans. Electron. Dev.* 53 (2006) 2328–2334, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TED.2006.881010>.
- [15] F. Siviero, et al., Design optimization of the UFSO inter-pad region, *Nucl. Inst. Meth. A* 1061 (2024) 169153, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2024.169153>.
- [16] S. Meroli, D. Passeri, L. Servoli, Energy loss measurement for charged particles in very thin silicon layers, *J. Instrum.* 6 (2011) P06013, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/6/06/P06013>.
- [17] L. Snoj, G. Žerovnik, A. Trov, Computational analysis of irradiation facilities at the JSI TRIGA reactor, *Appl. Radiat. Isot.* 70 (2012) 483–488, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2011.11.042>.